
D4.20 Cogwheel Workshop 6

WP4 Joint integrative projects

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: NVI

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Other contributors	Kristin Sæbø Pettersen (NVI)
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Report from Cogwheel Workshop 6 One Health EJP / SafeConsume

Introduction

In Work Package 4 (WP4) of the One Health European Joint Programme (OHEJP), EU initiatives that require strategic interaction with OHEJP are identified in collaboration with WP2 and WP5, to avoid redundancy and to further leverage the alignment at EU level. One of the instruments, so called cogwheel workshops (CWs), are being organised by WP4 to allow key actors and relevant partners within the OHEJP, typically Project leaders or WP leaders within Joint Research Projects (JRPs) or Joint Integrative Projects (JIPs), to identify synergies, joint priorities and opportunities for collaboration within the OHEJP or with other EU initiatives. Before contacting the relevant EU initiative/project, it is important to identify and collect (common) JRP and JIP needs and to define if the initiative complies with these needs. Furthermore, it is important to see if the initiative can complement or assist the OHEJP, for instance with database/repositories, protocols, advice, practical collaboration (sequencing, bioinformatics) and so on.

Eight CWs will be organised during the OHEJP. The reports from the CWs will be part of the input to the Strategic Research Agenda (SRA) of WP2, as well as the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of WP7. The CW will ensure that OHEJP development is complementary and that potential synergies are identified.

The target for the sixth CW was the SafeConsume project <https://safeconsume.eu/about/the-project>. SafeConsume is a research and innovation action funded by Horizon2020. It is a five-year project, now in its fourth year. The consortium consists of 32 partners from 14 countries in Europe, and is coordinated from Norway (Nofima). The budget is 9.5 mill Euro. The overall objective of SafeConsume is to reduce health burden from foodborne illness through changing consumer behavior.

Practicalities

- Information about the upcoming CW was sent to all OHEJP Project leaders and deputies and members of the Scientific Steering Board (SSB) on the 26th of October 2020. Information about SafeConsume was included.
- The invitation was also distributed to the OHEJP PhD projects and the new institutes and member states entering the OHEJP consortium from 2021.
- To reach even broader, the invitation was additionally distributed by the OHEJP key communication contacts (Jade Passey and Piyali Basu) and distributed to each member institutions through the respective Communication Contact Persons.
- SafeConsume highlighted COHESIVE, NOVA, DiSCoVer, TOXOSOURCES, ADONIS, EnvDis and SUSTAIN to be of special interest and these projects were specifically encouraged to participate in the CW with SafeConsume.

- The OHEJP members were asked to identify which WPs in SafeConsume to be of special interest. This information was forwarded to SafeConsume before the workshop.
- Deadline for registration was set to the 15th of November and the CW was held as an online meeting with 31 participants using Adobe Connect on the 25th of November 2020. The agenda is included in the annex.
- Six OHEJP projects signed up with presentations at the CW. Seven OHEJP projects were represented in total, including two PhD projects.
- The meeting was recorded until lunch. A link to the recorded meeting, the given presentations and contact information for follow-up questions was distributed after the CW.

Attendance list

Project	Representatives (institution)
SafeConsume	Rosie Allison Solveig Langsrud Tekla Izsó Paula Teixeira Anca Nicolalu
COHESIVE	Eduardo Costa (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research) Zuzana Nordeng (Norwegian Institute of Public Health)
MATRIX	Esther Sundermann (BfR)
ORION	Estíbaliz López de Abechuco (BfR)
TOXOSOURCES	Arno Swart (RIVM) Gereon Schares (FLI) Marco Lalle (Istituto Superiore di Sanità) Marieke Opsteegh (RIVM) Nadja Bier (BfR) Zuzana Nordeng (Norwegian Institute of Public Health) Pikka Jokelainen (SSI)
EnvDis	Laura González Villeta (University of Surrey)
SUSTAIN	Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden (Roskilde University)
NOVA	Jenny Frössling (SVA)
OHEJP Administration	Kristin Pettersen (NVI) Marie Nykvist (SVA) Lena Tuominen (SVA) Karin Artursson (SVA) María Ugarte Ruiz (VISAVET-UCM) Pikka Jokelainen (SSI)
OHEJP Communication team	Piyali Basu (University of Surrey)
Other	Ingrid Cardenas Rey (Wageningen Bioveterinary Research) Ciriac Charles (ANSES) Teresa Nogueira (INIAV - Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária I.P.) Giovanni Lo Iacono (University of Surrey) Gordon Nichols (PHE) Emma Gillingham (PHE) Joaquin Prada (University of Surrey)

Output

All OHEJP projects interested in participating in the CW had the opportunity to do so. The relevant key elements in SafeConsume, as identified by each OHEJP project, are listed below. The proposed action points from each project are listed in a separate summary table below.

Meeting summary, per project

Key elements in SafeConsume relevant for each One Health EJP project:

EJP Project	COHESIVE
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foodborne diseases • Disease prevention • One Health

EJP Project	MATRIX
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foodborne illness

EJP Project	ORION
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The content from the WP 4, 5, 7 and 8 regarding the tools for communication of food safety, risk policy models and the general dissemination of the project

EJP Project	TOXOSOURCES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Toxoplasma gondii</i> • Foodborne pathogens in general • Synergies and shared interest already identified, TOXOSOURCES are already in contact and collaborate with SafeConsume

EJP Project	EnvDis
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A risk behaviour map would be nice to have to analyse salmonellosis cases in those areas in particular. Any data related to food consumers actions/eating habits related to eggs and chicken would be really helpful for our project • It would be nice to have an open data exchange with SafeConsume as well as other projects within the OHEJP, even before publication

EJP Project	SUSTAIN
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of qualitative and quantitative analysis • Approach to education • Foodborne diseases and behaviours of consumers • Initiating food safety policy

Summary table Action points

Project	Action points	Who, when
COHESIVE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No action points identified 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The COHESIVE participants suggested direct contact with the COHESIVE project leader and SafeConsume leaders/management for

		possible follow up meetings
MATRIX	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contact SafeConsume regarding continuing the discussion about potential collaboration between SafeConsume and Knowledge-Integration Platform 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Esther Sundermann Done on 25.11.2020
ORION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Follow up the interest shown about OHS-Codex to continue the discussion about potential collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Esther Sundermann (MATRIX), Estibaliz López de Abechuco Soon
TOXOSOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Schedule next TC with SafeConsume Continue the Results Booster activities Share information to whole consortium 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pikka Jokelainen/Marieke Opsteegh/Marco Lalle Soon Pikka Jokelainen Ongoing Pikka Jokelainen When next communication
EnvDis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Include consumer habits on eggs and chicken on the model Find other major food sources of <i>Salmonella</i> Measure other determinant environmental variables influencing the incidence of disease 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Laura Gonzalez At earliest convenience (ideally early 2021)
SUSTAIN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keeping up-to date with the SafeConsume project, e.g. following via Twitter, following research outputs, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden Now

Other comments

- In general, the workshop and choice of project (SafeConsume) received positive feedback. The format is appreciated to get information about other projects.
- Discussions were actively ongoing throughout the workshop, including exchange of contact information. More time in the agenda for discussion was suggested.
- Impact on agencies, authorities etc is a critical issue, but difficult to measure. SafeConsume had included these aspects nicely in their project structure and design, and this is something the OHEJP should prioritize in the future.
- Exchange of information also within the OHEJP projects are highly appreciated at the CWs. The possibility to organize internal CWs (like ORION did) was underlined.
- The 6th CW was the first workshop including the PhD projects when distributing the invitation. The PhD students confirmed that the format is very suitable for presentation and scientific discussion training, and suggest to include the PhD projects in future CWs.
- TOXOSOURCES has already interactions with SafeConsume and was the OHEJP project suggesting SafeConsume for this workshop. This interaction is a good example of how two different projects can be nicely connected and aligned.
- Focus on collection and integration of data is important, but should also have a look into the detection and how to make Europe equally efficient in detection, to complete the picture.

TOXOSOURCES suggested to include OH-HARMONY-CAP and IMPACT (*Cryptosporidium* molecular detection in fresh produce as a model; Anne Mayer-Scholl is the Project coordinator) in the discussion.

- Asking the invited project to highlight which OHEJP projects were of special interest was considered a good initiative. The presentations are short and more like teasers. Maybe some of the OHEJP presentations should go deeper.
- More OHEJP projects could have been interested in seeing the presentation and perhaps more OHEJP projects would register for the CW if the detailed agenda was announced earlier.
- It was suggested that if presenters could be seen via video while presenting, this might make it easier to follow the presentations.
- Good opportunities for future cooperation were identified.

Concluding remarks

In general, the workshop format, content and choice of project (SafeConsume) received positive feedback and good opportunities for future cooperation were identified. Suggestions for improvements will be considered for the future workshops. However, it is challenging to cover all interests in one workshop and sub-categorization of different CWs might be a solution to consider.

Presentations given at the meeting

See Annex.

The recording of the cogwheel workshop can be accessed through the following link;
<https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/pe5zno1lm0gi/>

ANNEX

Cogwheel Workshop 6 One Health EJP / SafeConsume

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This meeting is part of the European Joint Programme One Health EJP.
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Agenda

One Health EJP

Grant Agreement number 773830

Date	25 November 2020
Venue	Virtual meeting ; https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/ohejp-cogwheel-workshops/
Meeting	Cogwheel Workshop OHEJP and SafeConsume

Meeting agenda

09:00 - 13:00 **Cogwheel Workshop (25.11.2020)**

09:00 - 09:10 **Welcome and presentation of participants**

09.10 - 10.30 **Presentation of SafeConsume and discussion**

- **09.10: Safeconsume & WP9 - Short introduction to Safeconsume (Solveig Langsrud; Solveig.Langsrud@Nofima.no)**
- **09.15: WP 2&3 (WP3 very short as results are confidential) - Hazards and Risks (Paula Teixeira; pcteixeira@porto.ucp.pt)**
- **09.30: WP 4&5 - Tools and food safety communication (Solveig Langsrud)**
- **09.40: WP6 - Development of educational programs for mitigating risk (Rosie Allison; Rosie.Allison@phe.gov.uk)**
- **09.55: WP7 - Food safety risk communication policy models across Europe (Tekla Izsó / Gyula Kasza; KaszaGy@nebih.gov.hu)**
- **10.10: WP8 - Spread the word on SafeConsume (Anca Nicolau; Anca.Nicolau@ugal.ro)**
- **10.20: Discussion**

10.30 – 11.30 **Presentation of OHEJP projects and discussion (10 min per project, including time for questions)**

- **10.30: COHESIVE – One Health Structure In Europe (Zuzana Nordeng; zuzana.nordeng@fhi.no)**

- **10.40: MATRIX – Connecting dimensions in One Health surveillance** (Esther Sundermann; esther-maria.sundermann@bfr.bund.de)
- **10.50: ORION - One Health Surveillance Initiative on Harmonization of data collection and interpretation** (Estibaliz Lopez de Abechuco; Estibaliz.Lopez-de-Abechuco-Garrido@bfr.bund.de)
- **11.00: TOXOSOURCES – *Toxoplasma gondii* sources quantified** (Pikka Jokelainen; pijo@ssi.dk)
- **11.10: EnvDis - Environment and Diseases: A general method linking Mechanism and Phenomenology** (Laura González Villeta; l.gonzalezvilleta@surrey.ac.uk)
- **11.20: SUSTAIN - Scientific UnderStanding of the policy process for Transboundary integration And INstitutionalisation of the One Health across EU member States** (Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden; sarahhd@ruc.dk)

11.30 – 12.00

Break

12:00 - 13:00

Separate meeting with only OHEJP projects, summary of discussions and follow up

Recording of the workshop can be accessed through this link:

<https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/pe5zno1lm0gi/>

Safeconsume – reduced foodborne illness by changing consumer behaviour

Solveig Langsrud, Scientific Coordinator

- Estimated 23 million persons get ill from foodborne disease yearly in Europe
- About 40% of illnesses are acquired from home
- Diarrheal food borne disease: 22 mill cases
- Top 5: Salmonella, Campylobacter, Toxoplasma, Norovirus, Listeria
- Salmonella&Campylobacter on the WHO high priority list for combating antibiotic resistance

Overall objective is to reduce health burden from foodborne illnesses

Changing consumers behavior to reduce exposure to hazards and decrease risk through:

- Effective and convenient tools and products,
- Communication strategies,
- Education,
- An inclusive food safety policy

Case studies

Five pathogens

- Salmonella
- Campylobacter
- Norovirus
- Toxoplasma
- Listeria

Four consumer groups

- Elderly
- Pregnant/ families with small children
- Teenagers
- Young single men

Meals

- Chicken and salad
- Eggs in hot or cold dishes
- Ready to eat: e.g deli meats, soft cheese, cut fruit
- Bivalve molluscs - oysters and clams

SAFECONSUME

What A multi-actor project (RIA) funded by the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

Who Coordinator: Nofima, Norway
Participants: 14 countries, 32 partners
Scientists, industry, organisations, authorities

When
2017-2022

Budget
9.5 mill Euro

SafeConsum structure

WP2&3: Hazards and risks

Paula Teixeira

WP2:

Effect of consumer behaviour on foodborne microbial hazards and evaluation of monitoring methods used by consumers to measure safety and performances

The key contribution of WP2 is/(was) to collect available data and generate new data needed to assess the impact consumer behaviour has on risk of foodborne diseases (WP3).

WP2:

Specific objectives

- Determine the impact of consumer behaviour on microbial reductions/growth/survival for each step-in food handling behaviour, from retail to consumption, through literature review and experimental work.
- Evaluate monitoring methods used by consumers to measure safety and performances
- Evaluate if consumer barriers for change identified in WP1 are scientifically sound
- Communicate a comprehensive overview of the impact of consumer behaviour and barriers on microbial reduction/survival/growth to science partners, market actors and policy makers in the project

WP2:

Critical consumer handlings (CCHs) from retail to consumption for five food-pathogen combinations often implicated in foodborne illness

Hazard	Food	CCHs domestic environment				
		Food choice	Inhibit growth	Kill/remove	Hygiene Protect	Pers. hygiene
<i>Salmonella</i>	Eggs Poultry	X	X	X		X
<i>Campylobacter</i>	Poultry	X		X	X	X
<i>Toxoplasma</i>	Vegetables and fruit	X		X		
<i>Norovirus</i>	Vegetables and fruit Bivalves	X		X	X	X
<i>Listeria</i>	RTE	X	X			
Stage ¹		All	T/S/P/Se	P	All	R/S/P/Se

¹ Stage in food chain. R: Retail, T: Transport, S: Storage, P: Preparation, Se: Serving

WP2

Month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	...	36
WP2	T2.1 Literature review and establishment of common test methodology																		-	
	T2.2 Effect of consumer behaviour on food safety: food choices and storage conditions																			
						T2.3 Effect of consumer behaviour on food safety: CCHs related to killing and removing pathogens														
						T2.4 Effect of consumer hygiene on spread, survival and elimination of hazards and evaluation of monitoring for assessing performance of hygienic measures														

Effect of consumer behaviour on food safety: food choices and storage conditions

TT2.1 Literature review and establishment of common test methodology

- The effect of consumer behaviours (documented in WP1 and from the literature) on microbial spread, growth and survival was reviewed.
- An overview of tools and technologies for food preparation and monitoring safety was prepared
- Plans and detailed procedures established

Effect of consumer behaviour on food safety: killing and removing pathogens

Task 2.3 CCHs related to Killing and Removing pathogens:

- **Effect of heating**

Salmonella in eggs and egg products

Monitoring done-ness of poultry

Monitoring done-ness of seafood

- **Effect of washing**

Consumer behaviours related to wash/ disinfect produce were tested for their efficacy against *T. gondii*, norovirus and *L. monocytogenes*

- **Barriers**

Barriers related to beliefs and skills that may lead to unsafe food handling were investigated

Effect of consumer hygiene on spread, survival and elimination of hazards and evaluation of monitoring ...

Task 2.4 CCHs related to Hygiene & Personal hygiene :

- **Cross-contamination and cleaning**

Effect of different documented consumer behaviours on bacterial spread or reduction were tested

- **Monitoring**

Hygiene monitoring behaviours were evaluated

- **Barriers**

Barriers related to beliefs and skills that may lead to insufficient hygiene were investigated

WP2

Results

- **Task 2.1** Literature review and establishment of common test methodology
- Information from scientific publications, risk assessment reports, technical reports, trade publications fed into Risk-Behaviour Map (149 entries) and linked to relevant CCHs
- Information on tools/technologies - mode of action, scientific validation, how could reduce risk, barriers to utilization - fed into the Risk-Behaviour Map (actually 103 entries in the map).
- Plans for experiments in tasks 2.2-2.4 established

WP2

Results

Measuring fridge temperature: tactile sense

- It is very difficult to discriminate the temperature of foods and surfaces
- The equivalent perceived temperature for the same intensity of coldness sensation is different for different foods and surfaces

Food Control 111 (2020) 107069

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Food Control

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/foodcont

WP2

Results

Preparing dishes with eggs

- Eggs should be stored in the fridge!
- What about shelf-life? Can I trust the "egg floating test"?
- No! Egg floating test does **not correlate** with **egg safety** and may even not correlate with **egg freshness**

WP2

Results

Preparing dishes with eggs

- Hard solid white and yolk assure that *Salmonella* was eliminated but...
- It is possible cook safe runny eggs and also save energy!

- Boiled 3 minutes
- Covered with water
- Rest for 10 minutes in the hot water (stove off)

5 log reduction

WP2

Results

Preparing dishes with eggs

- Non-heated egg dishes/desserts, why not?
 - But safer to use **pasteurized eggs!**
- For those who insist in preparing mayonese with raw eggs...
 - Mix the yolks well with a similar volume of vinegar and leave the mixture at **room temperature for >3 h** before adding oil and other ingredients
 - Better not use **backyard (raw) eggs**, at least in Portugal!

Food Control 113 (2020) 107180

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

Food Control

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/foodcont

Short communication

Occurrence of *Salmonella* spp. in eggs from backyard chicken flocks in Portugal and Romania - Results of a preliminary study

WP2

Results

Preparing dishes with eggs

- Following cooking instructions from the labels maybe not enough to assure that *Salmonella* will be completely inactivated. Survivors may grow especially if dishes are stored at abuse temperatures even though the dishes look good!

WP2

Results

- **Preparing seafood**
 - Spiked clams immersed in water at 90°C for 10 min (ensuring that meat reached 90°C for 90 sec) confirmed a log₁₀ reduction of 2.96±0.79 and 2.56±0.56, for GI and GII HuNoV (RTqPCR assays)
 - Heat treatments of bivalves which cause reductions >2.5 log₁₀ as measured by RTqPCR (ISO method) may be regarded as safe. !

WP2

Results

- Preparing dishes with poultry and vegetables
- 50% of vegetables (including for prewashed) from Portugal/Spain contained *Toxoplasma*.
- As washing processes do not remove completely the oocyst and these are not eliminated by chemicals, **pregnant women** should be advised about the risk if they are not immune to toxoplasmosis
- Washing vegetables thoroughly at home with antibacterial agents at appropriate concentrations can **reduce** the prevalence of pathogens (*L. monocytogenes*)
- A few drops of vinegar or lemon juice will have **no effect**
- Addition of sodium hypochlorite, peracetic acid (PAA), or chlorine dioxide **significantly enhanced** viral (norovirus) removal as compared with water alone.

Marques et al. Parasites Vectors (2020) 13:180
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13071-020-04040-2>

Parasites & Vectors

RESEARCH

Open Access

Detection of *Toxoplasma gondii* oocysts in fresh vegetables and berry fruits

 foods

Communication
Effectiveness of Consumers Washing with Sanitizers to Reduce Human Norovirus on Mixed Salad

WP2

Results

Preparing dishes with poultry and vegetables

- Using a food thermometer to measure thoroughness of poultry is **neither a safe procedure nor easy to implement** as food thermometers are often slow or inaccurate
- Using **core colour is not safe** as colour change occurs before bacterial kill

PLOS ONE

OPEN ACCESS PEER-REVIEWED
RESEARCH ARTICLE

Cooking chicken at home: Common or recommended approaches to judge doneness may not assure sufficient inactivation of pathogens

WP2

Results

Hygiene & Personal hygiene

- Hygienic cleanliness **cannot be measured visually**, and cleaning should be targeted to situations rather than based on routine or visual cleanliness
 - Sites with counts $>10\ 000$ cfu were in several cases evaluated as visually clean.
 - Some surfaces with <1000 cfu were regarded as visually very dirty

WP2

Results

Hygiene & Personal hygiene

- Brushes are more hygienic than sponges
- The hygienic condition of cloths and sponges is related to use and how they are stored between use (hang up or not) rather than storage time.
- Using antibacterial cloths/sponges do not reduce risk

- Hang it up!

- ...and change it if you use it to something dirty
brushes with chlorine, boiling or dishwasher may be a safe alternative to replacing them with new ones.

Cleaning of sponges and

International Journal of Food Microbiology 337 (2021) 108928

Contents lists available at ScienceDirect

International Journal of Food Microbiology

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/ijfoodmicro

Dishwashing sponges and brushes: Consumer practices and bacterial growth and survival

WP2&3: Hazards and risks

Paula Teixeira

WP3:

Survey based HACCP and probabilistic risk assessment

Objectives

- Develop a **survey-based HACCP approach** that allows the measurement of problematic consumer food handling practices in a standardised, quantitative and cross-nationally comparable manner
- Collect **representative data in ten countries**, covering the diversity of the regions of Europe (Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Spain, UK)
- **Rank consumer food handling practices** in demographic groups in terms of their impact on exposure and risk
- Provide subsequent WPs with an evidence basis for **prioritising risk mitigation and risk communication** efforts
- **Assess the impact** of personal and situational factors that modulate hazard or exposure, responsiveness to risk communication or adoption of technical innovations, and thereby operate as facilitators or barriers in the promotion of safer food handling practices
- Extend the survey-based HACCP approach towards a more **stringent quantitative risk assessment methodology**, using probabilistic techniques
- Estimate the **expected risk reduction effects** of changes in problematic food handling practices

WP3

WP overview

WP4&5: Tools and food safety communication

2017

2018

2019

2020

2021

2022

Mapping the Consumer Journey

Opportunity Map

How Might We?

Opportunities selected based on existing technology

Company 1 Company 2 Company 3 Company 4 Company 5 Company 6 Company 7

Selected opportunities for ideation and concept development

Design, technology & tools

Educational programs

Policy models

Communication strategies

Ideation session

The 10 teams selected 3 opportunities from the opportunity area map.

They brainstormed ideas and solutions, then clustered them and selected 3 to develop.

3 ideas were described and one favourite selected to present for the rest of the GA participants.

Idea
Fridge deposit revolution

Deposit intervention for encouraging consumers to get rid of old malfunctioning fridges and invest in new state of the art fridges.

Policy model + Service

Idea
4 finger rule

A simple rule to memories how to store leftovers safely.

Information + "Rule of thumb" + Could be integrated on products

AHO Student Projects

A: Awareness
F: Fear
E: Engaging

Ørjan Laxaa
Extendable kitchen:
Foldable countertop

Einar T- Lukerstuen
Verksytavle: cross
contamination **FE**

Morten Lerfold Overrein
Mobile cover: cross
contamination **F**

Agata Cypriak vel Czupryniak
Chopping board: cross
contamination

Martha Riznez
Chopping board fjøl: cross
contamination

Clementine Rusten
Frost: cooling leftovers

Ella Shegai
"Wash me" chpping
board **A**

Emma Wind
Stacking system: extendable
kitchen

Eilo Rishovd
Kitchen cloth: cross
contamination **A**

Glenn Sæstad
In Vitro Chicken Sashimi
Texturizer **A**

Kevin Andreas Ehrenberg
Lab Kitchen: cross
contamination **E**

Hanna Tørstad
Kitchen faucet: cross
contamination **A**

Natacha Dankrathok
Lukk - phone holder: cross
contamination **F**

Hanna Nordland
Chopping board: cross
contamination

Marte Rennemo
Food thermometer: cross
contamination (salmonella) **F**

Eirunn Marie Margaret Kvalnes
"Trace" chopping board: cross
contamination **FA**

Madeleine E. Kristiansen
Chopping "box": cross
contamination **A**

Hans Kristian Villa
Heatwave - box: cross
contamination & leftovers **A**

Suzanne Arnesen
Vispa: cross
contamination **AE**

Ida Lahm
Knife holder: cross
contamination **F**

Sarah C. Herland Andresen
Dishbrush: cross
contamination **A**

Kristian Haugvik
Gadget for food containers:
leftovers **A**

Lisa Siegel
Chopping board: cross
contamination

Åsmund Ivarjord
Water carafe: raising cross
contamination
awareness **FAE**

Max Armas Tomren
UV lamp: cross contimi-
nation &
sustainability **F**

Vilde Brabrand Urfjell
Perfectly cooked ham: food
poisoning **A**

Elizabeth B. Stein
Chopping board: cross
contamination **FA**

Innovative products to mitigate risk

Behavioural change app and market strategies

Designit

Overall aim WP5:

Improve Food Safety Communication

- To develop and evaluate a food safety myth reduction app
- To test how different risk communication strategies influence willingness to implement new food safety tools or procedures.
- To deliver scientifically proven risk communication strategy advice that can be applied by all stakeholders promoting food safety in the home.

Food Safety Myths: What do people believe?

We define **myths** as «cases in which people's **beliefs about factual matters** are **not supported by clear evidence** and expert opinions».

(Nyhan & Reifler, 2010)

Shopping

Storing

Hygiene

Preparation/cooking

Serving

Storing

Food Safety Myths: > 50% believe

- Nationally produced food is safer than imported food.
- Being too clean is the cause of allergies
- Home-made food is safer than industry processed food
- Hot food will be spoiled if refrigerated before cooling to room temperature.
- If the food smells and tastes fine it is safe to eat.

Behaviour is not only a matter of knowledge

CNN health Food Fitness Wellness Parenting Vital Signs

Edition ▼ 🔍 🌐

Who could make you eat undercooked chicken or moldy bread? Your future in-laws, research suggests

By **Katie Hunt**, CNN

🕒 Updated 0753 GMT (1553 HKT) June 29, 2020

Within intense social situations, such as that first visit to soon-to-be in-laws, people may feel compelled to eat high-risk foods, like undercooked chicken, in order to make a good impression, researchers in Norway have found.

(CNN) — Bloody hamburgers. Pink chicken. Moldy bread.

We all know these foods are risky and could make us sick, but research has suggested that in certain high-stakes social situations — like dinner with your prospective in-laws or a BBQ at your new boss' house — you may eat them anyway.

Risk Analysis, Vol. 40, No. 5, 2020

DOI: 10.1111/risa.13449

Situated Food Safety Risk and the Influence of Social Norms

Nina Veffen ^{1,6,*} Joachim Scholderer,^{2,3,4} and Solveig Langsrud⁵

Previous studies of risk behavior observed weak or inconsistent relationships between risk perception and risk-taking. One aspect that has often been neglected in such studies is the situational context in which risk behavior is embedded: Even though a person may perceive a behavior as risky, the social norms governing the situation may work as a counteracting force, overriding the influence of risk perception. Three food context studies are reported. In Study 1 ($N = 200$), we assess how norm strength varies across different social situations, relate the variation in norm strength to the social characteristics of the situation, and identify situations with consistently low and high levels of pressure to comply with the social norm. In Study 2 ($N = 502$), we investigate how willingness to accept 15 different foods that vary in terms

Report: Scientifically proven risk communication strategy advice

To be prepared

WP6: Education of teenagers

WP6: Development of educational programmes for mitigating risk

Rosie Allison, e-Bug Project Manager
Public Health England, UK

The project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement No 727580

SafeConsume: Education for secondary schools (11-18 yrs)

To develop and evaluate risk-based education programmes for secondary school children (11-18 yrs) aiming to increase primary knowledge, skills and awareness.

Needs
Assessment
2017-2019

Learning
Outcomes
2018-
2019

Resource
Development
2019-2020

Evaluation
2020-2021

Needs Assessment: Aim

- To understand students' and educators' knowledge, decision processes, skills, intentions and beliefs about capability and consequences around the topic of food hygiene and food safety.
- Qualitative data was applied to the **Theoretical Domains Framework (TDF)** and **Theory of Practices (ToP)** to determine:
 - where there are deficiencies in knowledge and skill
 - inform the development of educational resources to teach 11-18 year olds on food hygiene/safety

Student data collection

Qualitative data collection

- Focus group
- Interviews

Knowledge (*Competencies*)

SafeConsume- WP6 - Cogwheel Workshop 2020

The understanding and awareness of food hygiene and food safety

Knowledge	Topic	Quote
Lack of knowledge	Foodborne microbes	<i>Salmonella. I think that's the only one I know. (England)</i>
	Cross contamination	<i>When you touch meat and then touch vegetables (England)</i>
	Food hygiene rules	<i>Hand washing! For sure, that's very important. (Hungary)</i>
Varied knowledge	Food safety	<i>It's about food conditions, use by dates, it is ripe or unripe... (Portugal)</i>
	Food storage	<i>At home we don't put anything away...mum says we do it wrong. (England)</i>
Higher knowledge	Food labelling	<i>Best before is at its best before that date and then use by you have to use it up by that date (England)</i>
	Personal hygiene	<i>We have to tie up our hair, not to fall in the food. (Hungary)</i>

Skills (*Competencies*)

SafeConsume- WP6 - Cogwheel Workshop 2020

The ability acquired through practice to have good food hygiene and food safety

Topic	Key Findings	Quote
Cooking skills	Students reported basic cooking skills	<i>We cook easy meals. When it's only cooking spaghetti or fish fingers. (Portugal)</i>
Making food safe to eat	Students check that food is cooked properly	<i>How do you determine the end of cooking? When there is no more blood! (France)</i>
Reheating foods	Varied skills to identify whether food can be reheated; some did not take any precautions	<i>You can only reheat it once [leftovers] and then it's, bacteria starts to grow on it (England)</i>
Source of skills - mother	Skills are usually learnt from their mothers or grandmothers. Lack of skills to find reliable food information sites.	<i>My mum said: "so don't you know how to cook?" and I told her: No, I can only help out". But you can learn!" And then she teach us. (Portugal)</i>
Washing up	Older students felt that they have better washing up skills than younger students	<i>Well, when I cook, a kind of a hygiene mania occurs in me, and there is nothing that I don't wash... I sanitize and wash everything. (Hungary)</i>

Knowledge and skills allow us to identify deficiencies in young peoples competencies and derive learning outcomes

Learning outcomes developed

1. To understand that:
 - a) There are both useful and harmful microbes in food.
 - b) The harmful microbes in food can cause food poisoning
 - c) The risks and consequences of food poisoning.
2. To understand labels, packaging and storage of food (cold chain)
3. To understand the chain of infection and critical points for food hygiene (Farm to Fork).
4. To understand cross-contamination and how it occurs
5. To develop and normalise skills for everyday life to remain in good health:
 - a) Hand and personal hygiene
 - b) Food hygiene and preparation
7. All above learning outcomes and to understand healthy eating and identify the different aspects of food nutrition and microbiology,

Other social/environmental factors support these gaps in competencies and can help to inform the development of educational resources

Factors	Findings	Implications
Social influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural influence • Family influence • Media influence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Address myths • Discuss different environments include family/home • Recipe e-book
Reinforcement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Negative reinforcement • Positive reinforcement • Classroom routines • Reminders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case studies • Outbreak investigation • Examples of food poisoning • Embed food hygiene steps into routine • Repeat key messages by visual methods
Beliefs about capabilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ability to cook - less capable handling meat • Food hygiene rules - students believe they are capable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Practical lessons • Following or making a recipe to include food hygiene steps
Beliefs about consequences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food hygiene concerns in canteens or restaurants • Knowledgeable about high-risk foods • Knowledgeable about importance of handwashing • Lack of concern over food poisoning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Useful and harmful microbes continuum • Examples of food poisoning • Outbreak investigation

Educator data collection

SafeConsume- WP6 - Cogwheel Workshop 2020

Qualitative data collection

- Focus group
- Interviews
- Analysis of national curricula of each country

Summary of educator results

- **Varied educator knowledge, confidence and skills** to teach food hygiene and food safety topics to young people
- Felt they had a **role** to teach food hygiene and food safety to young people
- **Optimistic** to help change behaviour of students
- **Positive intentions** to teach these topics
- **Main barrier** to teaching food hygiene and food safety is the need for these topics to be embedded in the national curriculum
- Time, cost, lack of facilities and poor school hygiene facilities are some of other barriers educators mentioned.

Knowledge and skills allow us to identify deficiencies in educator competencies to inform a teacher training module

Resource development

Educational resources: Lesson plans

(11-14)
a) Teacher PowerPoint & Teacher Information Sheet

b) Student Worksheet

1. User Journey

2. Food safety vs food quality

3. Useful and harmful microbes

Case study: a cautionary tale

- In 2008, a 20 year old man in Belgium died 10 hours after consuming spaghetti with tomato sauce
- It had been left unrefrigerated at room temperature for 5 days and reheated in the microwave before consumption.
- The culprit: a bacteria called *Bacillus cereus* which can commonly contaminate rice and pasta

User journey

Educational resources: Lesson plans

(15-18)

a) Teacher PowerPoint & Teacher Information Sheet

b) Student Worksheet

1. Outbreak investigation

2. Food safety facts

Additional resources: All ages

Food safety pledge

CONTENT

Using this Book
Information for teachers

	Denmark Kiksekage Koldskål Sol over Gudhjem	7		Hungary C	B
	England Fish and Chips Herby Omelette	9 11		France Cordon Bleu Crème Brûlée Pan Bagnat	13 15 17

Food hygiene curriculum and learning
Acknowledgements

[Previous](#)

CHICKEN PAPRIKASH WITH DUMPLINGS (PAP-REE-CASH)

Chicken with paprika is an undeniable part of classic Hungarian cuisine. Suitable for any occasion, even birthdays or weddings. It is often eaten for lunch or dinner, all year round.

INGREDIENTS:

For the paprikash:	1 teaspoon of marjoram
4 chicken drumsticks	1 teaspoon of ground red paprika
4 chicken wings	1 bay leaf
2 onions	2 teaspoon of salt
3 cloves of garlic	175 grams of sour cream
100 millilitres of olive oil	2 teaspoons of flour
1 teaspoon of course black pepper	
For the dumplings:	100 millilitres of milk
2 eggs* (see footnote)	500 grams of flour
100 millilitres of cold water	A pinch of salt

Tools needed: chopping knives (x2), chopping boards (x2), large saucepan, frying pan, mixing bowls (x2), slotted spoon, whisk

Cooking techniques: stir-frying, boiling

*Use commercial/store-bought eggs or those that are known to come from *Salmonella*-vaccinated hens. In the UK, use eggs with the British Lion mark.

[Previous](#) [Next](#)

Recip-e-book

Dan Murray - Festival food seller

I sell basic food - chips, burgers, sausages - at festivals and fairs. People come to me when they've been out all day, eating picnics, drinking, dancing, going on fairground rides, using portaloos, all sorts! Then they come back the next day complaining that they've been sick and my food made them ill. Or maybe it could have been anything else they did all day, in fact all week?

Fact: *Campylobacter's* incubation period - the time it takes from eating infected food to being ill - is 2 to 5 days. *Listeria* usually takes about 30 days.

Issue: Most foodborne illnesses take a few days or weeks to make you ill, so people tend to think of the 'unusual' food they've eaten out in that time, and not the normal everyday food they've cooked at home.

Question: Can you think of everything you've eaten in the last 30 days? How much of it was out at a restaurant?

I'm a Scientist Get me OUT of here

Food safety debate kit

Teacher training

The teacher training modules have been developed to support educators with additional information aiming to boost knowledge and confidence in teaching about aspects of microbiology, foodborne infection and other aspect relating to food such as nutrition and food labels.

Modules designed as an information reservoir to allow teachers to choose the information they need.

The Four teaching modules include:

- Session 1: Teaching food hygiene - An introduction
- Session 2: Microbiological aspects
- Session 3: Food labels
- Session 4: Infection transmission

Each session links to the relevant student resources they prepare for.

The screenshot shows a digital interface for the 'SAFE CONSUME' project. On the left, a sidebar titled 'Teaching food hygiene: An introduction' lists five topics: Nutrition, Microbiology (highlighted in red), Ecology, Allergy, and Culture. A small purple microorganism icon is next to the 'Microbiology' item. The main content area is titled 'Microbiology' and contains a paragraph of text about food contamination, a video player with a play button, and a link to 'WHO : five keys to safer food video'. At the bottom, there is a 'World Health Organization' logo and a 'Microbiological risks' link. The footer includes the 'SAFE CONSUME' logo and navigation buttons for 'Close and go back to session 1', 'Previous', and 'Next'.

WP7: Food safety risk communication policy models across Europe

Gyula Kasza
National Food Chain Safety Office,
Hungary

WP7 in a nutshell

This work package aims to provide a **food safety risk communication framework** (a 'good practice document') **for authorities** in order to help them ...

- with scientifically proven **tools, messages for communication**
- to **improve their communication practices** for ensuring effective preventive risk communication towards consumers
- to **improve their connections to other actors** and stakeholders of the food safety system
- to **become a 'food chain safety knowledge center'** for the society

WP7 in a nutshell

To achieve the mentioned objectives, the activities in WP7 concentrate on:

- The mapping of currently used food safety risk communication models
- The best practices for consumer risk communication
- The mapping of networks between food safety authorities and other actors
- The best practices for collaborations between authorities and NGOs
- The integration of all relevant SafeConsume results from other WPs into the risk communication framework
- The cooperation with EFSA for presenting our framework to be an official recommendation for food safety authorities

The main problems of food safety authorities regarding communication

- Legislation can control the safety only in earlier stages (before consumers) of the food chain
→ consumer targeted communication is needed to affect consumers' food safety related knowledge, attitude and most importantly, behaviour
- Food safety related information cannot compete with high level of noise, even nutrition has higher priority
- Behavioral biases and limited rationality of consumer decisions

Stages of the progression of food safety risk communication

1. First step towards consumers:

Deficit model (1990s)

2. Bilateral communication appears:

Dialog model (mid 1990s)

3. The era of public participation:

Partnership model (late 1990s)

4. Understanding consumers' behaviour:

Behavioural insight in policy-making (end of 2000s - today)

SAFE CONSUME

„Beyond communication campaigns”

Behavioural insight in food safety risk communication

Principle: to modify human behaviour, we should consider that consumers act out of routine, often being not aware of the reasons for their actions

- Observational studies to identify the practical reasons behind behavioural patterns
- „Changing people’s behaviour without changing their minds”:
- Easy-to-understand, easy-to-remember quick hints on food safety that don’t require profound changes of habits and preferences
- Easily applicable solutions to be invented and integrated into consumer lifestyle
- Act before it is too late: by childhood education we could place good behavioural patterns before routine gets too deep

→ SafeConsume is built on these

Research on food safety risk communication policy models

Exploring the current European risk communication scheme in the framework of SafeConsume

Structure of the research:

- Two online surveys
 - Governmental organizations, authorities and other institutions
 - Non-governmental organizations
- Completed by interviews with relevant NGOs and literature review
- Output: European risk communication framework and identification of current best practices

Participants of the „authority” survey

- 34 countries
- 75 institutions
- Responsibilities:
 - Risk assessment 47%
 - Risk communication 57%
 - Risk management 51%
 - Food inspection 39%

Risk communication practices of authorities

Consumer risk communication group

Average FTE: 4

- Dedicated risk communication group
- General communications department dealing with risk communication
- Staff members engaged in risk communication but not primary job

Risk communication practices of authorities

Consumer risk communication groups' composition

- Journalism or PR
- Agricultural/food/horticultural engineering
- Veterinary medicine
- Microbiology
- Psychology/social science
- Marketing/business
- Human medicine
- Toxicology

Risk communication practices of authorities

Approaches

Risk communication tools

Out of the governmental food safety organizations

- ... 81.3% has an own website or posts on specific portals
- ... 68.8% is present on social media platforms
- ... 0.9% use paid exposures or advertisements
- ... 56.3% works with print journalists
- ... 59.4% works with TV journalists
- ... 59.4% works with radio journalists
- ... 62.5% produces own printed materials
- ... 68.8% produces own flyers or posters
- ... 1.9% operates applications for cell phones
- ... 53.1% has educational programmes

Risk communication tools: specific materials on the 5 hazards in focus of SafeConsume

... 46.9% has materials on *Listeria*

... 40.6% has materials on *Salmonella*

... 34.4% has materials on *Campylobacter*

... 18.8% has materials on *Norovirus*

... 18.8% has materials on *Toxoplasma*

Situation of non-governmental initiatives

- There are a lot of NGO types who are active participants of the European food safety risk communication system (e.g. consumer organisations, industrial federations, media actors, research institutions, educational institutions etc.)
- Usually, food safety is not their main topic to communicate on (e.g. nutrition, sustainability, personal hygiene are more popular)
- NGOs have less financial and human resources for communication - average FTE: 0.59
- Their expertise, their different tone and the potentially high reach of consumers should be better exploited

NGOs as communicators: how do they do it?

Communication with **authorities**

* pre-COVID

Channel	%
E-mail	58%
Face-to-face meetings	44%
Bilateral phone calls	31%
Telephone/video conferences*	22%

Communication with **consumers**

Channel	%
Own website	60%
Unpaid posts on social media	33%
Working with journalists	25%
Printed material	23%
Paid exposure on social media	8%

Food safety risk communication in Europe – conclusions on the current status

Traditional forms of risk communication continue to dominate

- One-way **deficit model** in consumer-directed communications
- Two-way **dialogue/ partnership model** in stakeholder communications

How can projects like SafeConsume inform and improve risk communication practices?

- **Behavioural insight:** targeting the consumer habits that matter
- **Prediction:** using the interventions and channels that are most efficient
- **Coordination:** linking authorities with the actors who can make things happen

SAFE CONSUME

WP8: Spread the Word

WP8

Objectives

- **Establish** and **use** active and competent systems for dissemination and exploitation
- **Enhance** the capacity building of individuals and institutions participating in the consortium
- **Communicate** food safety to consumers through strategies with documented effect on behaviour
- **Disseminate** documented strategies for helping consumers mitigate risk to relevant actors interacting with consumers (market, authorities, researchers and other stakeholders)

Dissemination Forum

SAFE CONSUME

WP8 – Social media

safeconsume.eu

safe.consume

Safe Consume

SafeConsume

@ safeconsume

Participation to conferences

Scientific
society

Talks

General presentation of the project

(Solveig Langsrud, *Senior Scientist* at Nofima, Norway)

European consumer perceptions and practices affecting food safety

(Silje Elisabeth Skuland, *Researcher* at Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway)

Using design thinking for safer food

(Antje Gonera, *Senior Scientist* at Nofima, Norway)

Education for food safety

(Magda Hann, *Project Assistant for e-BUG*, Department of Health from Public Health England, UK)

Food safety risk communication practices and networks across Europe

(Joachim Scholderer, Professor and Head of Academic Unit at the University of Zurich, Switzerland, and Gyula Kasza, Head of Department at the National Food Chain Safety Office, Hungary).

Scientific society

Scientific publications – successful stories

The screenshot shows a web browser displaying a PLOS ONE article. The article title is "Cooking chicken at home: Common or recommended approaches to judge doneness may not assure sufficient inactivation of pathogens". The authors listed are Solveig Langsrud, Oddvin Sørheim, Silje Elisabeth Skuland, Valérie Lengard Almlie, Merete Rusås Jensen, Magnhild Seim Grøvlen, Øydis Ueland, and Trond Mørretrø. The article was published on April 29, 2020. On the right side, there are statistics: 0 Save, 3 Citation, 4,995 View, and 7 Share. Below the article title, there are tabs for Article, Authors, Metrics, Comments, and Media Coverage. The Media Coverage tab is active, showing a section titled "Media Coverage of this Article" with a link to report additional coverage. Under "News Media Coverage", there is a link to a CNN article by Katie Hunt titled "How to tell if your chicken is cooked properly - CNN". Under "Blog Coverage", there is a link to a New York Times article titled "Your Chicken Is No Longer Pink. That Doesn't Mean It's Safe to Eat. - The New York Times". The browser's taskbar at the bottom shows several open PDF files and the system clock indicating 4:05 PM on 11/23/2020.

Scientific society

scientific publications – successful stories

The screenshot shows a web browser window displaying a CORDIS article. The browser's address bar shows the URL: cordis.europa.eu/article/id/423188-what-ails-in-european-kitchen-hygiene-and-food-shopping-habits. The page header includes the European Commission logo, the CORDIS logo, and the text 'EU research results'. A search bar is visible on the right. The main navigation bar contains links for HOME, RESULTS PACKS, RESEARCH*EU MAGAZINES, NEWS & EVENTS, PROJECTS & RESULTS, ABOUT US, and LOG IN. The article title is 'What ails in European kitchen hygiene and food shopping habits?'. Below the title is a sub-headline: 'Three EU-funded studies explore European kitchen cleaning habits and the food safety knowledge and practices of Romanian consumers.' There are language selection buttons for DE, EN, ES, FR, IT, and PL. A 'HEALTH' tag is present. A 'Related projects' section features a 'HORIZON 2020' logo and a project card for 'SafeConsumE: Safer food through changed consumer behavior: Effective tools and products, communication'. The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows several open PDF files and the system clock indicating 4:40 PM on 11/23/2020.

WP8 - Non scientific Publications”

Advice in a national language

SafeConsume to Romanians:

- To wash or not to wash poultry meat before cooking it?
- How to correctly store and cook eggs
- Can we avoid listeriosis?
- How to organize our fridges
- Norovirus - the virus who can ruin our winter holidays
- Do not trust your senses when comes to food safety
- How important is to wash our hands
- Self-care week in Europe

World Food Safety Day

Food safety is everyone's business

2019 - presentation of e-Bug in schools,
& washing hands in kindergardens
2020 - online event

Self-Care Week Europe 2019 & 2020

Promoter of the event: Lars Münter, RBH, Denmark

Subscribe to our newsletter:
safeconsume.eu

Thank you!

COHESIVE: One Health Structure In Europe

Zuzana Nordeng, Project Participant
Senior Adviser/One Health Coordinator at
Norwegian Institute of Public Health
6th Cogwheel workshop 25. November 2020
between SafeConsume and OHEJP

COHESIVE: One Health Structure in Europe

Mission statement:

COHESIVE aims to develop **sustainable One Health approaches** with respect to *signalling, surveillance, assessing and controlling zoonoses* at the national and regional level **within EU countries and across borders.**

Cooperation between 19 MedVetFood Safety Organisations from 12 countries in Europe

Sweden:

SVA: National Veterinary Institute Sweden
PHA: Public Health Agency
NFA: National Food Agency

Italy:

IZS AM: Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale dell'Abruzzo e del Molise
IZS LER: Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Lombardia e dell'Emilia-Romagna
ISS: Istituto Superiore di Sanita

Germany:

Bfr: The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment
FLI: Friedrich Loeffler Institute

France:

ANSES: French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety

United Kingdom:

APHA: Animal and Plant Health Agency

Czech Republic

VRI: Veterinary research institute

Belgium:

Sciensano (Public health and veterinary health institute)

Norway:

NIPH: Norwegian Institute of Public Health
NVI: Norwegian Veterinary Institute

Portugal

INIAV: National Institute for Agricultural and Veterinary Research

Austria:

AGES: The Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety

Denmark:

DTU: Technical University of Denmark

The Netherlands:

WBVR: Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
RIVM: National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (coordinator)

Objectives

1. Stimulating One Health approaches at the national level within EU countries (EJP partner member states) and focusing on strengthening human-veterinary collaboration
2. Roadmap towards an EU zoonoses risk-assessment of risk-analysis system
3. Design and test a common open source platform for the collection and analysis of surveillance and outbreak data on (foodborne) zoonoses
4. Capacity building within and between EU countries at several levels (executive level, communication, policy makers) within the area of zoonotic diseases.

Preliminary developments and results

EFSA: WGS

Cohesive information system
WP4.1

Webportal for tracing
WP4.2

Tool for quantitative risk modelling
WP4.3

Cost-benefit analysis FS
WP3.5

Surveillance data
Horizon scanning information
Event-based data

Learning from past outbreaks
WP3.3

Coordinated governance

Organising OHRAS
WP2.1

Formal & informal exchange of information (regional, national, international) WP3.1

Pilot
WP3.4

Decision tool for risk assessment tools
WP2.2

Pilots implementation OHRAS
WP2.3

Thank you for your attention!

@OneHealthEJP

/company/h2020-One-Health-EJP

OneHealthEJP.eu

MATRIX: CONNECTING DIMENSIONS in ONE- HEALTH SURVEILLANCE

Esther M. Sundermann, BfR
(WP 5 leader)

An Overview

- A Joint Integrative Project (JIP) under the One Health EJP
- Aims to:
advance the implementation of **OHS in practice** by building on **existing resources** while considering **different levels** of financial and infrastructural conditions

MATRIX Outputs

Pathogen-specific tracks: Campylobacter, Salmonella, Listeria, Emerging Threats (e.g., AMR)

MATRIX Outputs

Knowledge-Integration Platform (KIP)

- Develop a **web-based** Knowledge-Integration Platform that supports **knowledge exchange** between different MATRIX partners and stakeholders
- offers resources (e.g., tools/technologies/features)
- permanent access to project outcomes

Knowledge-Integration Platform (KIP)

[Home](#) **One Health Surveillance Codex Document**

latest

Introduction / Background

The Collaboration principle: Supporting OHS collaboration & cross-sectorial communication

The Knowledge principle: Improving the OHS knowledge base

The Data principle: Supporting OHS Data interoperability, integration & interpretation

The Dissemination principle: Supporting external communication of OHS outcomes

Summary and Outlook

Acknowledgements/Funding information

Abbreviations/ Acronyms

References

[Docs](#) » Welcome to the One Health Codex Document!

[Edit on GitHub](#)

Welcome to the One Health Codex Document!

KIP Population

MATRIX:

- Best practices and guidelines
- A self-assessment tool for OHS capacities (EUEpiCap tool)
- A roadmap to future develop or implement national OHS activities
- Dashboard for vizualisation

Suggestions are very welcome:
esther-maria.sundermann@bfr.bund.de

Why MATRIX?

	Hazard specific tracks			
	Emerging threats <i>(incl. AMR)</i>	Salmonella	Campylobacter	Listeria
WP1 - Existing frameworks and OH capacity				
WP2 - Best-practices and multi-sectorial collaboration				
WP3 - Output-based surveillance evaluation				
WP4 - EUEpiCap				
WP5 - Outreach and roadmap				
WP6 - Decision and collaboration dashboards				

WP0-Coordination

Thank you for your attention!

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OneHealthEJP.eu

ORION Project

Estíbaliz López de Abechuco

25th November 2020, Cogwheel workshop

The JIP Project “ORION”

One health surveillance Initiative on harmonization of data collection and interpretation

The ORION project aims at establishing and strengthening inter-institutional collaboration and transdisciplinary **knowledge transfer** in the area of **surveillance data integration and interpretation**, along the One Health (OH) objective of improving health and well-being.

Barriers for One Health Implementation in Europe

- High heterogeneity in numbers and types of national bodies involved
- Surveillance approaches (need to) differ greatly
- In general:
 - Cross-sectorial collaboration and knowledge exchange should be improved
 - Cross-sectorial communication should be improved
 - Solutions supporting cross-sector surveillance data interpretation needed
 - Interoperability of surveillance data should be improved
 - “Tools” supporting OH implementation in practice missing

What is needed ?

A resource to:

share practical resources and **experiences** (tools, technical solutions, guidance, lessons learned) to

improve integrated surveillance data analyses and interpretation across OHS sectors

the **One Health Surveillance (OHS) Codex**

The OHS Codex Principles

OHS Codex principles are the “**area of action**” applicable to any

- sector specific surveillance activity
- cross-sectorial surveillance activity

The OHS Codex Framework

Each OHS Codex principle has:

- Purpose description
- Scope description
- Methods / Tools – each with a short description and links
- Examples & Lessons learned

OHS Codex as a Read-the-Docs Web Resource

One Health Surveillance Codex Document
latest

Search docs

Introduction / Background

Purpose

Target community, main stakeholders and organizations

Scope

Principles

The Collaboration principle: Supporting OHS collaboration & cross-sectorial communication

The Knowledge principle: Improving the OHS knowledge base

The Data principle: Supporting OHS Data interoperability, integration & interpretation

The Reporting principle: Supporting external communication of OHS outcomes

Summary and Outlook

Acknowledgements/Funding information

Abbreviations/ Acronyms

References

Private repos and priority support
Try Read the Docs for Business Today!

Read the Docs v: latest

Purpose

The purpose of this OHS Codex is to provide users with guidance and resources, e.g. tools, technical solutions, guidance documents, that improve collaboration, mutual understanding and knowledge exchange between the different OHS sectors. Moreover, it is ought to support better surveillance data integration and interpretation, along the One Health (OH) objective of improving health and well-being. The OHS Codex thereby supports the ambitions outlined in chapter 3, 4, and 5.1 to 5.3 of the FAO, OIE and WHO document "Taking a Multisectoral, One Health Approach: A Tripartite Guide to Addressing Zoonotic Diseases in Countries" [10] (Tripartite Guide) by proposing specific resources that support putting a true One Health approach (as described in the Tripartite Guide) into practice.

Fig. 1: Connection between the Tripartite Guide and the four principles of the OHS Codex. The OHS Codex principles and their dimensions are indicated by coloured arrows. The icons correspond to the guiding icons from the Tripartite Guide.

Target community, main stakeholders and organizations

According to the understanding of the authors elements of the OHS Codex will be useful for organizations or researchers that are

Summary & Outlook

Achievements

- OHS Codex available at: <https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>
- Continuously updated (suggestions collected and curated by ORION team at https://docs.google.com/document/d/1UKM16rUeN4tRYY_RuYMULPR6v1rD2zaq8FXUDDJsbkw/edit?usp=sharing)
- Allows to share guidelines, tools, experiences or other useful resources
- A new cross-sectorial, EU focused, not legally binding resource nicely aligned with the Tripartite Guide

Current work

- Continuous integration of new resources and tools
- Integration of “lessons learned” from national ORION OH pilot activities
- OHS Codex will be extended / maintained within the JIP MATRIX project

Thank you for your attention!

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#TOXOSOURCES

Toxoplasma gondii sources quantified

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FOODBORNE TRANSMISSION PATHWAYS FOR *TOXOPLASMA GONDII*

Adapted from EFSA BIOHAZ Panel (2018)

LEGEND

Oocysts

Tachyzoites

Bradyzoite

Oocysts

Tachyzoites

Bradyzoite

TOXOSOURCES

Toxoplasma gondii sources quantified

2.5-yr Joint Research Project within One Health EJP

Project Leader: Pikka Jokelainen, SSI, Denmark; PIJO@ssi.dk

Co-Leader: Joke van der Giessen, RIVM, the Netherlands

North: Denmark (**SSI**, DTU), Sweden (SVA, SLV), Norway (NVI, FHI)

East: Poland (PIWet), Czech Republic (VRI, NIPH)

South: Italy (ISS), Spain (VISAVET-UCM), Portugal (INSA, INIAV)

West: The Netherlands (RIVM, WBVR), France (ANSES),
Germany (BfR, RKI, FLI), UK (UoS)

+ External partners and collaborators

<https://onehealthejp.eu/jrp-toxosources/>

TOXOSOURCES

Toxoplasma gondii sources quantified

Aims to address the question:

“What are the relative contributions of the different sources of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection?”

Different approaches,
including modelling and new methods

WP1 Coordination and impact

Pikka Jokelainen & Joke van der Giessen

WP2 QMRA for *T. gondii* infections

Marieke Opsteegh & Sara Monteiro Pires

WP3 Role of fresh produce

Marco Lalle & Anne Mayer-Scholl

WP4 Serology to discriminate infections via oocysts vs. tissue cysts

Furio Spano & Frank Seeber

WP5 *T. gondii* typing to detect within-genotype variation

Gereon Schares & Simone Cacciò

TOXOSOURCES

Toxoplasma gondii sources quantified

Aims to address the question:

**“What are the relative contributions
of the different sources
of *Toxoplasma gondii* infection?”**

Quantitative estimates of main sources of *T. gondii* infection

New data on role of ready-to-eat produce

New serology method to detect infections caused by oocysts

Novel typing method to trace outbreaks

- ✓ Gaps filled
- ✓ Collaborations across sectors
- ✓ Will enable development of evidence-based interventions

STATENS
SERUM
INSTITUT

Thank you for your
attention!

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A general method linking Mechanism and Phenomenology

6th Cogwheel Workshop

By Laura C. González Villeta

WP 6 EnvDis

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25th Nov 2020 - Virtual

Salmonellosis and climate: what are the main drivers of disease?

1. Scope of the project and applications
2. Methodology (mechanistic approach)
3. Current progress
4. Future work

1. Scope of the project and rationale

1. Scope of the project
2. Methodology
3. Current progress
4. Future work

Source: Public Health England (PHE)

- **Aim:** Identify environmental drivers of disease, and its contribution
- **Goal:** Estimate impact of climate change

1. Scope of the project
2. Methodology
3. Current progress
4. Future work

2. Methodology: mechanistic model

1. Understand bacterial growth
 - Egg: Yolk membrane breakdown time → Exponential growth rate *Salmonella* (FAO, 2002).
 - Chicken: Nmax in chicken breast (with initial low density of *Salmonella* ($10^{0.6}$ CFU) (T.P. Oscar, 2006).
2. Expected number of infections for a given time, area, and number of residents.
3. Recorded data:
 - Salmonellosis in England and Wales (PHE)
 - Climate data (MetOffice)
4. Compare simulated cases with recorded data

➔ Result: check the suitability for seasonal predictions of our model

3. Current progress: predictions vs epidemiological data

- 1. Scope of the project
- 2. Methodology
- 3. **Current progress**
- 4. Future work

Comparison of sources of salmonellosis. Years 1989-1995

— Reported cases PHE — Simulated cases from chicken — Simulated cases from eggs — Temperature

3. Current progress: predictions vs epidemiological data

50-50 Weight of sources of salmonellosis. Years 1989-1995

- 1. Scope of the project
- 2. Methodology
- 3. **Current progress**
- 4. Future work

3. Current progress

50-50 Weight of sources of salmonellosis. Years 1989-1995

Assumptions:

- Normalized cases
- Cases proportional to bacterial growth
- Distribution of cases

Disregards:

- Eating habits
- Human behaviour
- Reporting delay

Result: suitability of seasonal predictions of our model

1. Scope of the project
2. Methodology
3. **Current progress**
4. Future work

1. Scope of the project
2. Methodology
3. Current progress
4. **Future work**

4. Preliminary conclusions & Future work

- 7 years analysed → Broader time analysis
- **Eggs** and **chicken** are a good proxy for seasonality → Include other food sources (?)
 - Simulate cases with more climate parameters
- **Temperature** seems to have a big influence on seasonality of salmonellosis → Check our seasonality predictions for a conditional incidence (e.g. $RH+T^a$)
 - Simulate effect of climate change
- Averages for England and Wales → Find possible geographical effect
→ Display seasonality in different countries

Thank you for your attention!

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SUSTAIN

Scientific **Under**standing of the
policy process for **Trans**boundary
integration **And** **IN**stitutionalisation
of One Health across EU member
States

Sarah Humboldt-Dachroeden

PhD fellow

sarahhd@ruc.dk

Social science meets natural science

- Aim: To understand the political drivers and constraints for integration and institutionalisation of the One Health approach across EU member states.
- But why?
 - Considerations of socio-political, socio-economic contexts.
 - Social science research has tools to investigate relations and examine them (e.g. social or policy network analysis; Interviews; surveys).
 - Understanding of institutions, understanding of perceptions - National and local realities.

Qualitative research interviews

- Cases: Sweden & Italy
- To understand institutional context and reveal perceptions of experts working in the field.
- Expert interviews
 - Sweden: Veterinary Agency, Public Health Agency, Food Agency and Environmental Agency
 - Italy: Veterinary Agencies, Public Health Agency and Environmental Agencies

Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Italy%E2%80%93Sweden_relations#/media/File:Italy_Sweden_Locator.png

Survey

- Planned spring 2021
- Online survey addressed to OHEJP consortium, stakeholders and ministries
- Understanding policy- and decision-making processes for One Health.
- How does knowledge transfer work -> Science to Policy?
- What needs to be improved for One Health policy integration?

Source: <https://onehealthjp.eu/consortium/>

Preliminary results of interviews

“So then I realised that all of us are talking about One Health surveillance but none of us really knew what it was and that it was just this abstract concept.”

(Veterinary Agency)

“[...] I have been trying to develop these contacts, but the interest hasn't been really great from the agency, from my agency, to develop a work area on this.”

(Environmental Protection Agency)

“Don't try to guess that you understand the other sectors data. Ask them, come together and when you put the data or analysis together, discuss it together to understand what it stands for.”

(Public Health Agency)

“[Share] what they are doing well, why and how this can be put in practice, what has been done and how it was done”

(Veterinary Agency).

What to do with this information?

- Preventing barriers and embracing opportunities for One Health
- Clarifying needs of actors involved in One Health projects
- Successfully implement future One Health projects
- Facilitate policy integration of One Health
- Promoting health of animals, humans and the environment

Thank you for your attention!

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